

THE ROLE OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article presents the important aspects of the use of technology in education and allows students to conduct the educational process more effectively. In recent years, rapidly developing technology has also affected the field of education. As a result, technological devices began to be used in education and teaching methods changed.

Key words: phone, electronic board, tablet, technology, smart technology, educational portal.

Many technological changes, such as the emergence of the Internet, the development of phones and tablets, have also affected the field of education. Therefore, we can say that the continuation of courses online, the emergence of the concept of distance education, and the use of smart boards in classes are the result of the use of technology in education.

The use of technology in education is the use of technological tools in education in any field. In this article, I also touched on the role of technology in Turkish education and in our own education. For example, education uses many elements of technology such as smart boards, projectors, and online learning systems.

There are many advantages of using smart technologies in education, but due to a number of problems, we cannot fully use these technologies. The first of these is that not all regions in our country are equipped with modern information and communication technologies. insufficient skills.

Although the process of assimilation of technology is a painful stage in developing societies, the reflection of technology in living spaces has also caused difficulties. Inadequate infrastructure, economic disparity, security concerns, and the use of foreign technology consumption are the causes of these problems.

The use of technology in education can be used as a teaching method and can vary depending on the content of the education. For example, in oral lessons, preparing and presenting slides is a more functional method, while in numerically oriented lessons, lecturing on a smart board and showing students animations leads to more effective learning.

Technological changes have also changed the field of education, and classrooms are using smart boards and projection devices. New technological tools have begun to change the teaching and learning environment. Strengths of using technology in education in Turkey:

1. Easily controls central exam systems.
2. Provides distance learning opportunities.
3. A significant spread has been achieved.
4. Teachers learn quickly.
5. It was especially useful as a learning support material in schools without a library.
6. Teachers; Access to students and parents has become easier with features such as the Internet and e-mail.
7. Passing exams has become easier.
8. Correspondence of the school administration has been facilitated.
9. Employees will be notified of official correspondence, changes to the curriculum and regulatory documents.

The first technology used in our education system was the telegraph. In 1882, with the introduction of electrical courses into the curriculum, the name of the Darushshafaka schools was changed to the School of Telegraph Science. This school greatly influenced the creation of telegraph infrastructure. It is also the first significant technology introduced by the civilian sector (Tekeli, 1983: 469).

The process of using computers in education; In 1984, it began with the purchase of microcomputers in secondary educational institutions as part of the "New Information and Communication Technologies" research conducted by the Ministry of National Education. In the academic year 1989-1990, attention was paid to the necessary research on the application models of computer-assisted education, and pilot programs on this topic were widely launched. After these studies, the number and types of computer-related courses and seminars conducted by the Ministry of National Education increased until 1999 (Yıldız, 2002).

In the 2003-2004 Turkey Electronic Transformation Project short-term action plan, the following activities were planned:

- open a school to the world, connect it to an Internet company;
- organization of 4,000 information technology classes in primary schools;
- creating a prototype of the educational portal;
- update of school curricula in order to effectively use information technologies in order to increase the quality and efficiency of education;

- conducting preliminary studies and taking necessary measures to open information technology training areas to the public in educational institutions.

Currently, the use of technology in education is growing rapidly in our country. For example, teachers have almost stopped teaching by writing on the blackboard as before, instead many have switched to teaching using slides prepared by teachers. The following can be cited for the use of technology in education:

Examples of using technology in education:

- use of electronic boards in classes;
- passing lessons through animated videos;
- course processing according to the online education system;
- teaching according to the distance education model;
- passing lessons through slides with the help of a projector;
- conducting live lessons via the Internet;
- passing lessons through YouTube videos;
- creating virtual classrooms;
- training through pdf files;
- watching lessons via phone and tablet;
- emergence of online educational platforms;
- use of augmented reality applications in education;
- use of laboratory equipment in the educational process;
- observing with a microscope in science classes;
- Teaching using interactive methods.

Although the use of pedagogical technology is often discussed through information technology, the use of any technological tool in education, whether simple or advanced, can be cited as one of these examples. For example, all types of equipment used in school laboratories can be described as technological devices.

The importance of using pedagogical technology is to ensure that students learn the necessary information faster and more effectively. The use of pedagogical technology is also important because it allows the teacher to conduct the lesson faster without writing the necessary information on the board. The use of pedagogical technology creates a modern education system. The use of technology in the lesson not only increases students' interest in the lesson, but also helps to stay ahead of technological progress.

Positive impact of pedagogical technology (technology) on education:

- technology allows students to develop research skills;
- it helps to increase the student's activity in the learning process;
- it ensures that students with different learning styles are not overlooked;
- technology brings a more effective and faster learning process in education;
- technological changes allow teachers to conduct lessons more easily;
- helps make lessons more interesting.

Modern smart boards have been brought to all higher education institutions at the initiative of our president. This makes a great contribution to the development of the education system. I think that if general education schools also switch to this system, students' mastery of lessons and interest in lessons will increase significantly. By the decision of the President, special attention is being paid to improving the qualifications of pedagogues. As a result, in the future, all pedagogues will teach using modern smart technologies, and the quality of education will increase even higher.

Today we are witnessing the rapid development of technology. The rapid development of technology affects all aspects of our lives. While this influence was initially welcomed as it made our social life easier, over time, technology began to become an integral part of our lives rather than an element that made our lives easier.

Along with all the elements that make up the social structure, education is one of the structures affected by technology. Education forms the basis of the stage of realization of goals for the future of society. As technology has become an integral part of life, training individuals to use technology effectively and efficiently becomes an important step towards the future.

In conclusion, Pedagogical Technology has many positive effects on education and the use of Pedagogical Technology continues to be widespread as it facilitates the learning process.

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